

Website Vulnerability Detection: Inception of Mitigation of Advanced Persistent Threats

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Abstract: There are four basic stages of Advanced Persistent Threat attacks Study, Spear, Search and Sabotage. The study stage is executed with intent to acquire as much information as possible about attack target through various methods. One of the most successful methods is to gather the vulnerabilities of the target website. To counter the APTs the very basic solution is to detect the vulnerabilities present in the website and build an attack proof website to further shorten the chance of APT attacks. Vulnerability is a weakness that exists in the computer component upon exploiting which the attacker can adversely affect on integrity, confidentiality and availability of the computer component. This paper presents the methods of detecting the website vulnerabilities and methods of eliminating them. The vulnerability detection could be the most profitable method in the direction of preventing the APTs attack.

Introduction: Common Vulnerabilities and Exposures (CVE) that maintains a system of information security vulnerabilities operated by Mitre Corporation, defines a vulnerability as “A weakness in the computational logic (e.g., code) found in software and hardware components that, when exploited, results in a negative impact to confidentiality, integrity, or availability. Mitigation of the vulnerabilities in this context typically involves coding changes, but could also include specification changes or even specification deprecations (e.g., removal of affected protocols or functionality in their entirety).” National Vulnerability Database (NVD) provides a detailed database on CVE dictionary vulnerabilities. And Common Weakness Enumeration (CWE) maintains a list of software and hardware weakness types as tree structure where in which each weakness is identified by a unique id. CWE has listed all publicly available weaknesses that could be exploited by the APT’s. CWE provides a detailed view of weaknesses form point of view of software development, hardware design as well as research concept. The vulnerabilities pertaining to website are listed down with fine granularity, like “Incorrect Privilege Assignment”, weakness id 266 with further refined weakness named “use of web link to unstructured target with window.opener access”, weakness id 1022, the weakness “Files or Directories Accessible to External Parties” with id 552 has many subordinate weaknesses, like “storage of file with sensitive data under web root” id 219, “unparsed raw web content delivery” id 233, “storage of file with sensitive data under FTP root” id 220, “use of persistent cookies containing sensitive information” id 539, “sensitive cookie without ‘HttpOnly’ flag” id 1004, “direct request (forced browsing)” id 425 are few to name.

The website shall be cross checked for all these weaknesses to confront the attacks from APT. Though the most popular and publicly known weaknesses are addressed by these (CWE, CVE and NVD) systems the developer may do fall fool to the attacks since the APTs are persistent and are executed for over a long period of time there shall be methods to detect and prevent these vulnerabilities to safeguard the website from being attacked easily. In spite of advanced vulnerability detection and prevention systems exist there are evidences proving the pitfalls in the website that may lead to attacks. This job of detecting the vulnerabilities is hard if not impossible. To avoid vulnerabilities the easy steps are to update the application, using the web application firewall and to use a malware scanner. Apart from these techniques there is a more secure method of avoiding the attacks is to use legal consented web penetration testing to acquire all the vulnerabilities that are liable to attacks. Penetration testing has proven to be the better remedy to explore the weaknesses present in the website. There are a bulk of penetration testing tools available in the Linux Kali version which are open source and easy to manage and operate. Some of them are, information gathering tools like netdiscover, Sparta, nmap. The vulnerability analysis tools like nikto, voiphopper, etc., web application analysis tools like burpsuit, commix, skipfish, sqlmap, wpscan. Spoofing and sniffing tools like macchanger, wireshark, responder, etc., all these tools could be unethical if done with the intention of attacking but could also be used with ethical consent of the institution to detect the vulnerabilities present in the website. All these tools are open source and have well structured reporting feature that help protect a in-house website from being fall prey to attacks by APTs. The good part of these tools is that they are open source that help identify, the way in fact the hackers and APTs do gather the weaknesses and vulnerabilities of an organization, through accessible source code. They provide insight into the way the APTs could identify the vulnerabilities to attack. The reporting system let the defender to point out all the exploitable vulnerabilities that he need to refine and rebuild or at least redefine the way the website is to be organized. In the following sections the different methods of detecting the web site vulnerabilities are discussed with brief flavor of prevention too.

Related work: “Extenuating Web Vulnerability with a Detection and Protection Mechanism for a Secure Web Access” by K. Vijayalakshmi, Dr. A. Anny Leema, has proposed a mechanism to protect the web site by using policy filters with WPS mechanism. This paper tries to eliminate the XSS attack and a safe web page for the user. “Anomaly Detection of Malicious Users’ Behaviors for Web Applications Based on Web Logs”, by Yang Gao, Yan Ma, uses web logs and clusters them based on the web browser behavior and with help of clustering machine learning algorithms extracts four major attributes from the dataset and predicts the probability of web attack and it suggest a better true positive value based on the log collected from the network and browsing logs. “WAVE: Black Box Detection of XSS, CSRF and Information Leakage Vulnerabilities” by Hamed Soleimani, Mohmmad Ali Hadavi, Arash Bagherdaei, proposes a tool to detect the potential attacks like CRPF, XSS and information leakage vulnerabilities. Using the three different case studies it been shown that the WAVE model has less false negative rate. “Detection and Removing Cross Site Scripting Vulnerability in PHP Web Application”, by Abdalla Wasef Marashdih, Zarul Fitri Zaaba, it tries to eliminate the vulnerabilities from the PHP page using the genetic algorithms in concentration with XSS attacks. Its checks the jsp and PHP pages to eradicate the found threats from the pages for secure working of the website. “Detecting Various SQL Injection Vulnerabilities using String

Matching and LCS Method”, by Anitha.V, Supha Lakshmi.A, Revathi.M, Selvi.K, performs detection of SQL injection on the database of websites for stealing sensitive data. The paper proposes two algorithms Brute-Force String Matching Method and Longest-Common Subsequence algorithm to protect database details and proves that the SQL injection could be stopped. “PHP Vulnerability Detection Based on Taint Analysis”, by Kai Cao, Jing He, Wenqing Fan, Wei Huang, Lei Chen, Yue Pan uses PHP parser syntax parser to detect the vulnerabilities present in the PHP code of the website of PHP5.2 and onwards to avoid the propagation of invalid input to output that can lead to adverse effect on the security of the website. “Automated Web Application Vulnerability Detection With Penetration Testing”, by Priyank Bhojak, Vatsal Shah, Kanu Patel, Deven Gol, works on different web application vulnerabilities like Broken Access Control, Insecure Configuration Management, SQL infusion, XSS and proves that it is not harder to detect and prevent the web application attacks with bit of sensitive coding. It use some popular penetration testing to detect these vulnerabilities. “A Framework for Web Application Vulnerability Detection” by Asra Kalim, C K Jha, Deepak Singh Tomar, Divya Rishi Sahu, prposes a taint style attacks detector that detects web attacks like Xss and SQLIAs and profoundly can manage to prevent the attacks.

Website vulnerabilities: vulnerability as defined by CVE leads to compromise of security of whole data of the website and user details of the website. The publically known vulnerabilities that CWE has listed are very severe and most likely to be used by attacker. As per OWASP the popular vulnerabilities are

a) Cross-Site Request Forgery (CSRF) Here genuine user authenticated web application from a website receives a request from a malicious website. The intruder accesses the compromised web application that has been authenticated by a user. The usual fallen fool services are net banking, network devises with web interface, trending social media, etc., As net banking fraud are increasing day by day let us consider at example of this sector. With some advertisement or mislead link if a bank customer happens to click on a malicious link in a fraudulentwebsite.com, that contains the reference of targetbank.com with a feature of net banking usually with facility for 3rd party fund transfer. This framed attack is intended to transfer Rs99999.00 to some account XXXXXXXXXXXX. This attack could be made successful with a simple anchor tag in the fraudulentwebsite.com as `Do you like the page?`. As soon as the authenticated user click on this link the request is sent to targetbank.com from the user browser to transfer Rs99999.00 to account XXXXXXXXXXXX that take the user to surprise only after he receives a fund transfer message from the bank.

b) SQL Injection: The target database receives a malicious SQL query that the attacker is trying to execute from the compromised website that has access to this target database. The SQL query could be executed at the back end without the knowledge of the either DBA or the clients of the database. The injection could happen on any database like MySQL, SQLServer, Oracle etc.,. The intention of the attacker could be extract the sensitive data like personal details, intellectual property or business or corporate confidential data. It can bypass the application security measures and policies. The SQL injection could be illustrated with following example. Say an attacker want to achieve the administrative privileges so as to get into the database and to control the database activities. Suppose the target website has an input filed for username and password to validate the user. And the

webpage code if looks like `loginname=request.POST['loginme']`
`securitycode=request.POST['securitycode']` `sqlquery="select userid, password form dbusers`
where `username=" ' "+ loginname +" ' and securitycode =' " + securitycode +" ' "`
`databasename.execute(sqlquery)` This code is vulnerable to SQL injection. The
attacker can easily bypass the validation with simple password field inputs as "*somepassword OR*
1=1" When the last statement of the vulnerable SQL code executed by the
`databasename.execute(sqlquery)` statement the sqlquery's where clause will be treated as TRUE
since `OR 1=1` is always TRUE. And the attacker will get the list of dbusers detailed list where
generally the topmost record will be of the database admin which will be listed.

c) Broken Authentication and Session Management: This is a vulnerability that allow the attacker to compromise the user password, credential keys, session details and cookies stored on a website. These can occur due to flaws in the authentication and session management of the website code. If one select a sign in page and check the source code the complete HTML code will be displayed along with the credentials for example as shown below

```
<div id="login">                                <p>Enter login details</p>
<form action="/site/signin.php" method="POST">                                <p>
<label for="loginname">Loginname:</label> amtheone <input type="text" id="loginname"
name="loginname" size=25 />                                </p>
<p>                                <label for="securitycode"> Securitycode:
</label> doyouknowme                                <input type="password"
id="securitycode" name="secutirtycode" size=25/>                                </p>
<button type="submit" name="form" value="submit">Login</button>                                </form>
</div>
```

Here in the page source one can observe that the cookie has stored the username (*amtheone*) and the password (*doyouknowme*) along the login session details. This could lead to attack if the session details are stolen.

d) Cross Site Scripting (XSS): is different from other vulnerabilities in the sense that it does not evade directly into the target rather it injects a malicious code to the target website and the users of the website will be the one at the receiving end. If not managed properly it may produce devastating effects on the user data, sessions and even sensitive information of the user could be at risk. There are two types of XSS attacks one is stored and other is reflected XSS. The example for the reflected XSS is that suppose the invader inputs a script into the search area of the vulnerable website as `<anytag attribute="value1/value2">send('XSS'); </anytag>`. If the website is vulnerable it displays the same message saying 'not found' and its URL will read as same malicious script. Now the attacker can embed any malicious code to the website to gain the target source from the website.

e) Unvalidated Redirects: The vulnerable website will accept and malicious input that has a URL to redirect to some other website. The unvalidated redirect and forward may lead to devastating results. The attacker user controlled input may contain URL that resemble to the genuine website URL so the user just redirects the link that ends up in a malicious website that may steal the user sensitive data.

This attack may lead to phishing attack that may cause a huge worth for the user. The following jsp code receives the GET request that redirects to some other URL without validating the URL.

```
public class SomeServlet extends HttpServlet {  
void receive (HttpServletRequest requ, HttpServletResponse resp) throws ServletException,  
IOException  
{  
    StringBuffer req = request.getQueryString();  
    if (req.equals("somewebsite"))  
    {  
        StringBuffer nextwebsite =  
            request.getParameter("somewebsite");  
        response.sendRedirect(somewebsite);  
    }  
}  
}
```

A website shall never have a servlet code that redirects a URL without validating and without confirming its genuineness.

f) Security Misconfiguration: This vulnerability has many sub flaws like storage of file containing sensitive data under web root, letting the sensitive data to embed into externally accessible file or directory, producing error messages having sensitive information, execution with irrelevant privileges, incorrect granting of permission to critical components, etc,. Let us take the most irresponsibly used vulnerability that is producing error message having sensitive information. Though the system has thrown an exception the logic shall not let the processed data shall reach the attacker as error information. Consider the following java database code.

```
StringBuffer loginname=request.POST['loginname']  
passcode=request.POST['passcode']  
:  
:  
public void getEmpDetails(String loginname, String  
passcode)  
{  
String query =""; try{ query="select empid, salary, pf, loanamt from employee where empname=  
"+ loginname + " and passcode =" + passcode;  
:  
dbname.execute(query);  
}  
catch(SQLException e)  
{  
System.out.println("These is an exception "+query);  
}  
}
```

The query string contains the complete result of execution of the query and if this data is shown as part of error message there could be security vulnerability.

g) Failure to Restrict URL Access: If a website cannot restrict a user for accessing a non accessible page this leads to failure to restrict URL access. When an attacker forcefully accesses a hidden page or restricted page that are not referenced by the website this is called forced browsing. The vulnerability that exists because of improper access control security policy implementation by the web application. The portion of the web page been protected from unprivileged user from viewing it. If somehow one get into the details of the restricted page then the access control policy of the web

site is at risk. Consider the following example
restricted from access

```
href="somepagelink.html">Restricted page</a>  
</div> <table>;;;;</table>
```

<div> The protected contents,

<a

```
<div id="restricted" style=display:
```

</div> as someone try to

click on this link the link lands in no mans area. But if the style attribute of the div tag is altered as text rather than none then the contents will be displayed by carrying the link forward. This is vulnerable since the access control policy is not strictly implemented.

h) Insecure Cryptographic Storage: This flaw is the result of the insecure software development lifecycle. As the counter part the secured information shall have been stored encrypted from external access. Protecting sensitive data is the primary goal of a web application. This vulnerability is listed by CWE under weakness id 813.

Vulnerability Detection: As there are umpteen number of vulnerability detection tools available this paper prefers Kali Linux Nikto tool. This tool covers majority of the web vulnerabilities detection ethically with consent of the website authorities. A sample execution of Nikto on a DVWA website has the following result.

```
- Nikto v2.1.6  
-----  
+ Target IP:      xxxx.xxxx.xxxx.xxxx  
+ Target Hostname: www.xxxxxxxxxxxx.com  
+ Target Port:    80  
+ Start Time:    2020-09-16 10:52:46  
(GMT5.5)  
-----  
+ Server: Apache  
+ The anti-clickjacking X-Frame-Options  
header is not present.  
+ The X-XSS-Protection header is not defined.  
This header can hint to the user agent to  
protect against some forms of XSS  
+ Uncommon header 'x-redirect-by' found,  
with contents: WordPress  
+ The X-Content-Type-Options header is not  
set. This could allow the user agent to render  
the content of the site in a different fashion  
to the MIME type  
+ Root page / redirects to:  
https://www.xxxxxxxxxxxx.com/  
- Nikto v2.1.6/2.1.5  
+ Target Host: www.xxxxxxxxxxxx.com  
+ Target Port: 80  
+ GET The anti-clickjacking X-Frame-Options  
header is not present.  
+ GET The X-XSS-Protection header is not  
defined. This header can hint to the user  
agent to protect against some forms of XSS
```

```
+ GET Uncommon header 'x-redirect-by'
found, with contents: WordPress
+ GET The X-Content-Type-Options header
is not set. This could allow the user agent
to render the content of the site in a
different fashion to the MIME type
+ GET /webmail/blank.html: IlohaMail
0.8.10 contains an XSS vulnerability.
Previous versions contain other non-
descript vulnerabilities.
+ GET /securecontrolpanel/: Web Server
Control Panel
+ GET /webmail/: Web based mail package
installed.
+ GET /cgi-sys/Count.cgi: This may allow
attackers to execute arbitrary commands
on the server
+ OSVDB-3233: GET /mailman/listinfo:
Mailman was found on the server.
+ OSVDB-2117: GET /cpanel/: Web-based
control panel
+ OSVDB-3092: GET /img-sys/: Default
image directory should not allow directory
listing.
+ Scan terminated: 20 error(s) and 7
item(s) reported on remote host
+ End Time: 2020-09-16 10:59:36
(GMT5.5)
-----
-----
+ 1 host(s) tested
```

As the report generated the found vulnerabilities are anti-clickjacking, XSS, Redirecting, improper setting of X-content header type, unclosed port 80, accessibility to secure control panel, command injection, insecure directory listing. Each of these vulnerabilities could be devastating in sense that the APTs could get hold of these weaknesses and could target the website for invasion. Nikto has many attributes for penetration testing. It supports SSL, has ability to predict the sub domains, it can perform almost all set of vulnerabilities, apart from root directory it can predict the any directory, checks for common parking site, has complete HTTP proxy, scans for non updated servers, multiple port scanning, can penetrate through all kind of servers like Apache, Nginx, HIS, OHS, Litespeed, OSVDB-3233, 2117, 3092 vulnerable Databases, webmail blank HTML having XSS vulnerability, MIME type content rendering etc.,

Mitigating the threat from vulnerabilities: Clickjacking is the kind of hijacking the user by eluding him to click on a multiple transparent pages or an invisible link that lead the user to a completely different un intended page or unauthorized page or domain. These have many social media example where the user is made to like or forward or share the page or link unintended. This could be countered with CSP-Content Security Policy method. The .htaccess or httpd.conf file shall be modified as follows

```
ServerName some-page.com ServerAlias www.some-page.com
Header always unset X-Frame-Options Header set X-Frame-Options "SAMEORIGIN"
```

To avoid the ease of invading of the attacker one can simply do remove the server version from the response headers in the httpd.conf file alter the server signature, this will reduce the risk of falling prey to attacker

```
ServerTokens Prod
ServerSignature Off
```

To eradicate the directory listing of the root directory the following modification shall be done in the httpd.conf file

```
<Directory ..... >Options
None/Indexes </Directory>
```

The multipart MIME boundary and inode number kind of sensitive information shall be safe guarded from attackers who could access it from Etag header, to overcome this vulnerability the httpd.conf shall be altered

```
FileETag None
```

The HTTP request methods which are by default set to many types available shall be controlled accordingly. Set the httpd.conf file to avoid this threat

```
<LimitExcept GET POST HEAD> deny from all </LimitExcept>
```

The Cross Site Tracking vulnerability can avoided by setting the httpd.conf file with addition of this tag

```
TraceEnable off
```

this can avoid the attacket from stealing the cookie and session information from the website browser.

The cross site scripting (XSS) attacks can be nullified by making these changes in the httpd.conf file

```
Header edit Set-Cookie ^(.*)$ $1; HttpOnly;Secure Header set X-XSS-Protection "1;mode=block"
```

by setting the header tag attribute to HttpOnly and Secure the XSS attack can be mitigated.

The website shall be SSL secure for which the default configuration shall be modified to get better security. Add these lines to the http-ssl.conf file to strengthen

```
SSLCertificateFile
SSLCertificateChainFile
SSLCertificateKeyFile
```

Future work: Detection of vulnerabilities in the website if is the beginning of mitigation of APT attacks the next process shall be the prevention of these vulnerabilities so that the website could be kept out of the reach of APT attackers. The future work is to build a framework which can automate the prevention of these vulnerabilities form the web application and website.

Conclusion: The work needed to detect the vulnerabilities in the website and web application is only possible through an automated tool that can identify the potential flaws in the web application. This paper has detected and proposed very effective measures to prevent these active vulnerabilities.

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